

COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH IN TEACHING PHYSICS IN TECHNICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

U.N.Sultonova

Termez University of Engineering and Agrotechnology, Ph.D., Professor

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Abstract. *The issue of Education is a process that is constantly adapting to the requirements of the Times and improving in harmony with the achievements of Science and technology. One of the peculiarities of the educational system of the 21st century is the demand for students in higher education institutions to be able to apply the knowledge gained in life, the improvement of their DTS and programs, in other words, the absorption of a competency approach into the content of the educational system, the achievement of its educational results is an urgent topic.*

Keywords: *competency, improvement, institutions, institution, creative, thinking, teaching. Theory, practice, physics, education, research, development.*

Introduction. The aim of the competency-based approach to teaching physics in technical universities is to develop students' creative thinking in relation to the study of physics, introduce information technologies in teaching professional competence, ensure harmony between theory and practice in teaching, improve the quality and effectiveness of education and the possibilities of educational services, create a regulatory framework for training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market, in-depth teaching of subjects, create an effective mechanism for the implementation of scientific and innovative achievements in practice. This means that improving the methodology of teaching physics in higher educational institutions based on the competence-based approach is a relevant topic, so this study can be a solution to the problem.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 19, 2021 No. PP-5032 "On measures to improve the quality of education in the field of physics and the development of scientific research" defines priority tasks for "improving the quality of education in the field of physics and the development of scientific research". To do this, it is necessary to improve the content of the methodology of teaching physics based on the competence-based approach.

In his Address to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted that "If we look at history, we will see that physics was the fundamental basis for the creation of almost all discoveries and technologies in the world. After all, without a deep understanding of the laws of physics, it is impossible to achieve results in such complex areas as mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, information technology, water and energy saving technologies."

Methodology. Based on the analysis of materials on the competency-based approach in education, the following information can be provided. The words "competence" and "competence" first began to appear in scientific literature. For example, in relation to linguistic theory, the term "competence" can be cited as an idea of the American linguist N. Chomsky, expressed in his work "Aspects of the Theory of Syntax": "Competence is a fundamental difference between a person

who knows, speaks and hears his language, and a person who uses it (in particular, actually uses it)" or "a person's ability to perform any activity."

G.A. Asilova, summarizing the definitions of the concepts of "competence" and "competence" in her dissertation, asserts that "competence" is the effective application of personal qualities, knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of activity in a certain area; He defined "competence" as an existing and potentially emerging ability to perform a certain activity.

J.E. Usarov in his scientific works defined competence as "experience and knowledge in a certain area or direction, manifestation of readiness to carry out activities, the ability of a person to successfully act in various non-standard situations."

According to B.Kh. Khodjaev, "competence serves to integrate self-development efforts aimed at mastering new personal experience."

N.A. Muslimov emphasizes that competence is not the acquisition of individual knowledge and skills, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent area.

Many scientists and specialists have expressed their opinions on the concepts of competence and competency. For example, in his monograph "Competence in Modern Society" J. Raven states that "competence consists of a large number of components, many of which are relatively independent of each other, some components relate more to the cognitive sphere, others to the emotional sphere. Components can complement each other in effective self-management."

It is worth noting that there are cases when the term "skill base" is used as a synonym for the concept of "competence."

This set of components allows a person to set goals, achieve success and develop in a given field of activity. Based on these concepts, we can come to the following conclusion. Competence is a manifestation of experience and knowledge in a certain area or sphere, readiness to perform activities, a person's ability to successfully act in various non-standard situations. This definition of competence indicates the knowledge and experience that a person has acquired in the learning process.

In education based on a competency-based approach, the student becomes the main participant in the educational process, having his own goals and objectives. This approach involves the student in active, conscious activity, develops information, communication, educational and cognitive skills, personal potential, and forms self-esteem (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Interrelation of elements of professional competence of a student.

A student's abilities are demonstrated through his competence. The totality of qualities, motivation and abilities of a student can be represented in vector form as follows, and its composition can be analyzed as a totality of knowledge, abilities, skills, qualifications and professional competence (Figure 1.2).

The goal of teaching physics based on the competence-based approach in technical universities is limited by the goals of DTS and the curriculum and connects the knowledge, skills and competencies of the student with an understanding of the purpose and means of implementing the competence-based approach.

Figure 2. Vector form of student competence.

Based on the above, various points of view on the concept of competence prove that this concept should be interpreted as a complex structure.

The formation and development of competencies in students can be divided into the following three types:

1. Meta-subject competencies (core competencies).
2. Interdisciplinary competencies.
3. Competencies related to the subject.

The accelerating pace of change in the labor market, the globalization of the information environment and the inability to meet the requirements for students with the old approach are as obvious as day.

Competence requires constant enrichment of one's knowledge, learning, perception of the demands of the time and the application of skills in finding new knowledge in one's practical activities. A competent specialist has the ability to choose appropriate methods for solving problems, reject inappropriate ones and look critically at the problem. Technical competence is a set of personal qualities of a technical specialist. If future technical specialists are armed with basic, general and special competencies, they will begin to look for new innovative experience, create scientific foundations for new creativity, innovative ideas, and on this basis, society will be able to become an innovator in the development of technologies.

Monitoring the results of education based on the competency-based approach, that is, assessing the student's readiness after graduating from a technical university to apply the acquired

knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies in familiar and unfamiliar life situations. Therefore, the use of the competency-based approach in each technical university serves as a solution to current problems.

Based on the analysis, we can say that the word "competence" comes from the word "Competence", which means "to compete", "to argue", "to compete" or "to be able to compete". Competence is a set of knowledge, skills, abilities and personal characteristics that leads to personal results and systematic activity. If we consider the relationship between competence and competency, it becomes clear that "competence" is primary, and "competency" is secondary. According to this ethical teaching, a person develops competence in a certain area, and based on the interaction of competence and competencies, a person is considered competent.

Figure 1.3. The relationship between the concepts of competence and competence in traditional education

Figure 1.4. Interference between the concepts of competence and competence

According to scientific psychological and pedagogical sources, competence is extremely complex and multifaceted. Therefore, its interpretations differ in content. The concepts of "competence" and "competency" pay special attention to the following: practical application of a set of knowledge; education, qualities and abilities of a student; readiness for practical activities; the ability to achieve the necessary results in solving problems in practice; creation by the student of a source of knowledge necessary for his activities.

Based on the continuity and consistency of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the priority of the personality and interests of the student, as well as in accordance with his age characteristics, the following basic competencies are formed:

communicative competence; information literacy;

competence in self-development; competence in the field of social activity of citizens; national and intercultural competence; mathematical literacy, awareness and ability to use scientific and technological innovations.

The ability to use and apply the knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies acquired by students in physics in everyday life, in understanding discoveries, scientific innovations, solving theoretical and practical problems, as well as to observe and understand physical processes and phenomena (mechanical motion, interaction of bodies, motion of a material point in space, rotational and translational motion, molecular-kinetic theory, gas laws, movement of liquids and gases, evaporation, boiling, laws of condensation, real gas laws, properties of solids, thermal phenomena, vibrations and waves, electrification of bodies, interaction of charges, short circuit, the Earth's magnetic field, phenomena of electromagnetic induction, solar and lunar eclipses, change of seasons, movement of planets, observation of meteors) and the application of knowledge.

By providing students with knowledge based on a competency-based approach, all departments of the Physics discipline prepare students to solve problems arising in their future specialty, using existing theoretical knowledge (see Table 1):

Table 1

Physical competencies are formed as follows:

	Departments of Physics	Mechanical phenomena
	The main theoretical part	Fundamentals of kinematics in the connection of the subject of "Physics" with other disciplines. General information about mechanics. Coordinate system - rectilinear motion of a point. The main task of dynamics is Newton's laws, the law of universal gravitation, conservation laws in mechanics. The law of conservation of mechanical work, energy, power, momentum. The structure of a rocket. Conditions for equilibrium of bodies. Mechanical vibrations, harmonic vibrations. Spring mathematical and physical pendulums. Mechanical waves, transverse and longitudinal waves. Poynting vector. Sound waves
1	Competence in observing and understanding processes and events	Mechanical motion, interaction of bodies, transmission of pressure in liquids and gases, observation of mechanical vibrations and waves
	Measuring and determining quantities	Measuring and determining time, distance, speed, mass, density, force, pressure, work, energy, period and frequency of oscillations
Competencies	Explaining processes and events	Mechanical motion, interaction of bodies, pressure transfer in liquids and gases, Newton's laws, laws of universal gravitation. Laws of conservation of momentum and energy. Hooke's law
	Conducting experiments and drawing conclusions	The path traveled in a straight line and uniformly accelerated motion. Conduct experiments and draw conclusions to demonstrate the dependence of the elastic force on the extension of the spring, the friction force on the normal pressure force, and the equilibrium conditions of the lever.
	Explain the principles of operation of physical devices and the structure of technical objects	Stopwatch, length measuring device, scales, dynamometer, barometer, hydraulic press, operation of simple mechanisms

Strengthening theoretical knowledge and applying physical knowledge in practice	Rectilinear, accelerated, rotational, and progressive motion. Newton's laws, Universal gravitation laws. Weight, elasticity, friction forces. Solving problems to consolidate knowledge about mechanical power, energy, momentum, torque, simple mechanisms, mechanical vibrations, waves, using electronic development and electronic textbooks from popular science literature, the Internet, and other tools. Measuring time, distance, speed, mass, work, and power. Applying knowledge, skills, and competencies from Newton's, Pascal's, and Archimedes' laws in everyday life.
Thermal phenomena	
Required learning materials	Structure of matter, thermal motion of molecules, temperature, ideal and viscous fluid. Bernoulli's equation. Poiseuille's formula, molecular-kinetic theory, isoprocesses. Maxwell's distribution, internal energy, laws of thermodynamics, real gases Van Der Waals equation. Conversion of gases into liquids Joule-Thomson effect. Amount of heat. Average kinetic energy of thermal motion of molecules, Barometric formula. Boltzmann distribution
Competencies Observing and explaining processes and events	Matter, change of state of aggregation, flow of liquid through a pipe, Poiseuille's formula, thermal motion, thermal motion of molecules
Determining the numerical values of physical quantities	Measurement of temperature, heat content, specific heat capacity, and air humidity
Explaining the physical nature of processes and phenomena	Changes in the aggregate state of matter. Atomic-molecular structure of matter, laws of thermodynamics, laws of conservation of energy
Conducting experiments and drawing conclusions	Temperature change during heat transfer, isoprocesses, thermal motion of molecules. Adiabatic process, crystal lattices
Explain the working principle of physical devices and the structure of technical objects	Thermometer structure, psychrometer, internal combustion engine, steam turbine structure

Strengthening theoretical knowledge, practical application of physical knowledge	To consolidate the theoretical knowledge gained on the size and mass of molecules, amount of substance, molar mass, the basic equation of molecular-kinetic theory, amount of heat, and specific heat of combustion of fuel, solve problems, complete test tasks, use scientific literature, the Internet, electronic development, electronic textbooks, and virtual laboratories. Study the melting and solidification of solids, internal energy and work, evaporation and condensation
Electromagnetic phenomena	
Educational materials	Electrification of bodies, Coulomb's law, Gauss's theorem, electrostatic field potential. Capacitance, capacitors. The existence of electric current in conductors. Ohm's and Joule-Lenz's laws, magnetic fields, Biot-Savart-Laplace laws, Lorentz and Ampere forces
	Magnetic field of matter. Types of magnets. Law of electromagnetic induction, inductance, transformers, Maxwell's equations for the electromagnetic field. Electromagnetic oscillations, electromagnetic waves. Poynting vector
Process and event tracking	Electrification of objects Interaction of magnets. The effect of a magnetic field on a current-carrying conductor. Thermal effect of current. Observation of electromagnetic induction.
Measuring and determining quantities	Measurement of current, voltage, electrical resistance, resistivity, work and power of electric current
Explaining processes and events	Interaction of charged bodies, effect of a magnetic field on a current-carrying conductor, thermal effect of current, electromagnetic phenomena
Conducting experiments and drawing conclusions	Experiments on series, parallel, and mixed connections of conductors, and the dependence of current on voltage in a section of a circuit
The working principle of physical devices and their practical application	Current, voltage, electrical resistance, Ohm's law for a part of a circuit, series and parallel connection of conductors. Voltage, electrical resistance, relative resistance. Application of the knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired in the work and power of electric current, the transformation of alternating current in life and technology.

Results and discussion. The sections of physics, optics, atomic and nuclear physics are studied by dividing them into competencies. So, students in physics should know and be able to apply: concepts, physical quantities, physical laws, physical phenomena that need to be explained, measurement, obtaining results, demonstration of theoretical knowledge, independent search for information, application in practice, student competence in physics, observation of processes and phenomena, measurement and determination of quantities, explanation of processes and phenomena, conducting experiments and drawing conclusions, the principle of operation of physical devices, application of physical knowledge in practice.

Competence is the ability to apply existing knowledge, skills and qualifications in everyday activities. It is important to create a pedagogical environment that affects the comprehensive development of the student (see table 2).

Table 2

Creating a pedagogical environment that affects the comprehensive development of the student.

Creating a pedagogical environment that influences the all-round development of the student	The knowledge and skills that students need to master include thinking, understanding the world, researching it, studying its processes, the relationship between events, situations, laws, and rules, etc.
To implement: “I want to”, “I can do it”, “I feel satisfied”, “They like me”	
Within the framework of this approach, we talk about the comprehensive development of the individual, the sphere of activity, and the emotional state.	

To organize the development of students' minds, it is necessary to see each achievement, for this it is necessary to offer such tasks and issues that the student can complete.

Students should feel the need to read additional literature, get acquainted with it and prepare, and understand that the need to gain knowledge is based on the ability to create large technical projects and implement it in life

It is advisable for a physics teacher to conduct his own psychological tests. In particular, tests such as “Aspiration in academic activity”, “Achieving success”, “Who are you?”, “What are you like?”, “Understand yourself”, “Evaluate yourself” are said to be the most priority areas that determine the student's thinking. For example, comparative tests. Tests such as “Can you describe the scientific idea innovations of your thought?”.

As a result, the student feels what is changing in himself. All the student's mental states change. For example, it causes a positive change in the perception, perception, concentration, memory, impression and thinking process.

As a result of the analysis of the above descriptions, knowledge can be defined as a product of research and thinking activities, creative processes in various forms, in a systematic, interdisciplinary and generalized manner. A comparative analysis of education based on the traditional and competency-based approach is as follows. Table 3. The desire to independently learn knowledge, in higher education institutions, students learn to find solutions to problems.

Table 3

Comparative analysis of the traditional and competency-based approach.

T/r	Didactic elements of the educational process	Traditional approach	Competency Approach
1.	Aims	Aimed at developing knowledge, skills and competencies	Competency development oriented
2.	Educational programs (educational content)	Implements state educational standards	Individual trajectory of actions aimed at mastering vocational educational programs
3.	Forms of organizing education	The amount of teaching hours is organized in the amount of 60% in the classroom and 40% outside the classroom.	Working individually and in frontal view
4.	Methods of organizing and implementing the pedagogical process	Traditional teaching methods within the classroom system	Non-traditional methods focused on an individual and competency-based approach
5.	The role of educators in the process of activity	"Advisor", "informant", "evaluator"	"Partner", "advisor", "assistant", "mediator"
6.	The role of learners in the activity process	"Listener", "receiver", "rememberer"	"Partner", "experimenter", "researcher", "constructor-creator", one who applies the acquired knowledge in unfamiliar situations
7.	Educational institution management structure	The structure is aimed at operating a technical higher education institution.	The structure is aimed at developing a technical higher education institution.
8.	Use of educational development technologies	Educational technologies serve to develop knowledge, skills, and competencies	Develops competence in practical activities and the ability to creatively approach transitions from one situation to another
9.	Monitoring and evaluating learning outcomes	Aimed at checking the formation of knowledge, skills and competencies	Aimed at determining the level of development of a specialist's professional and personal qualities

In addition to studying the student's personality, science teachers should also know the methods for determining the level of development of competencies in the application of acquired

knowledge, skills and abilities in their work. These issues are resolved through psychological and pedagogical diagnostics and fully cover the educational process. It has the following areas.

1. Evaluation of learning outcomes. 2. Study the quality of teaching. 3. Planning the next stages of the learning process. 4. Encourage their achievements in learning and teaching. 5. Optimization of the learning and education process. The tasks of diagnostics are as follows: 1. Determining the relative progress of students.

2. Analyzing changes in the level of development as a result of certain influences.

When forming the professional training of future engineers-technologists, it is necessary to take into account the following factors:

1. Behavioral model. The inner state of the soul and the system of spiritual and moral views of future engineers-technicians are reflected in their behavior, actions, manners. Therefore, role models are an important factor in the educational process, influencing the professional training of future technical specialists.

2. The future engineer-technician carries out communicative activity, forming a sense of identity in the process of professional activity. In an environment without movement there can be no activity. Therefore, ensuring the effectiveness of the development of professional training of future technicians also depends on the factor of action.

3. The methodology is introduced into the consciousness of the engineer through specially organized verbal communication. Verbal communication is carried out between the objects of the educational process and acts as a factor in the process of forming the professional training of the future technical specialist.

4. The effectiveness of training is determined by the attitude of the teacher and the future technical specialist to their activities.

5. Characteristics of the content, forms, methods and means of teaching.

6. Social factors: humanization and democratization of the educational process, independence, freedom, transparency and equality.

7. Regional factors: content, richness, historical role and significance of the cultural values of the region of residence of engineers-technicians.

When teaching natural sciences, competencies in fundamental and natural sciences are conditionally selected.

Table 4

Competencies based on the curriculum

Communicative competence	The communicative competencies that need to be formed should be reflected in the subject.
1. Being able to ask and answer questions logically based on the topic, knowing one's native language and one foreign language	1. Knowing the names of physical concepts, such as: amount of substance, specific heat capacity, and using them in communication.
2. Being able to follow the culture of communication in communication, being able to work in a team, analyzing the interlocutor's opinion, and defending one's position.	2. Being able to clearly and clearly state the definitions of laws (gas laws, light refraction, refraction) (isothermal, isobaric, isochoric) orally and in writing.
3. Being able to control one's passion in various conflict situations, reacting	3. Being able to logically ask and answer questions based on one's knowledge of the

<p>to disagreements fairly, honestly and positively, and making the necessary decisions</p>	<p>relationship of concepts related to the subject with the sciences.</p> <p>4. Being able to respect the interlocutor's opinion on the subject and work on the basis of mutual agreement.</p> <p>5. When solving problems, making decisions based on physical phenomena and laws in various tasks</p>
<p>Information literacy</p> <p>1. Ability to use and communicate with existing information sources (Internet, television, radio, audio, video recordings), telephone, computer, e-mail, and messaging.</p> <p>2. Create and analyze databases in YEXSEL.</p>	<p>The reflection of the competence of working with information that must be formed in the subject of study</p> <p>1. Ability to work with various information sources: books, dictionaries, popular scientific literature, newspapers and magazines, the Internet, electronic development, electronic textbooks, television, radio, computers, e-mails.</p> <p>2. Search for and find the necessary information on each topic. Ability to write a term paper and an abstract on a given topic.</p>
<p>Competence of self-development as a person</p> <p>1. Self-development as a person.</p> <p>2. Ability to feel the responsibility of working in groups, be a leader, make decisions in various problem situations.</p> <p>3. Striving for physical, moral, spiritual and intellectual perfection.</p> <p>4. Ability to demonstrate abilities depending on one's interests, participate in science Olympiads, competitions.</p> <p>5. Possessing human qualities such as honesty and truthfulness.</p>	<p>The competence of self-development as a person that needs to be formed is reflected in the subject of study.</p> <p>1. In order to develop oneself as a person in the study of this subject, independently prepare an abstract and a term paper on the works and topics of scientists who have contributed to science</p> <p>2. Be able to independently perform laboratory work, experiments in science and draw conclusions.</p> <p>3. Be able to demonstrate interest in science based on what they have studied and try to create new technical projects related to science</p> <p>4. Be able to participate in various events, gain respect and solve problems encountered in everyday life.</p>

<p>Socially active citizenship competence</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Feeling of responsibility towards the homeland. 2. Not being indifferent to the events taking place in society, expressing one's attitude. 3. Understanding the essence of one's profession and consciously striving for the future. 4. Compliance with labor and civil relations, economic, environmental, legal culture. 	<p>The socially active citizenship competence that needs to be formed is reflected in the academic subject.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To feel one's place in technical higher educational institutions, neighborhoods and public places and to create innovative ideas and implement ideas for life 2. To be able to objectively evaluate the advantages of one's own essays on the subject and independent work. 3. To help one's comrades in technical higher educational institutions, to participate in discussions with them, to be generous to those in need.
<p>Universal cultural competence</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Carefully preserving the historical and spiritual heritage of our people, respecting their rituals and traditions. 2. Knowledge of national ideology, national universal human principles and tasks. 	<p>Reflection of the universal human competence that needs to be formed in the subject of study.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Being loyal to the Motherland by being kind to people. 2. Showing creative abilities, creating various models, puzzles, new innovations. 3. Studying the place of physics among other sciences, its history and development paths. 4. Respecting the worldview of others
<p>Mathematical literacy, knowledge of scientific and technical innovations and their use</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Be aware of and be able to use scientific and technical innovations that facilitate human labor, increase labor productivity and create favorable conditions. 2. Be able to interpret the reform of development, the five principles and seven priority areas, and have information about the place of our country in the world community. 	<p>The mathematical literacy that needs to be formed, awareness of scientific and technical innovations, and the reflection of the competence of use in the subject of study.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Be able to show the results of one's activities based on accurate calculations 2. Be able to draw drawings, graphs, and pictures using formulas in everyday activities. 3. Be able to work with various measuring instruments. 4. Be aware of innovations in the development of science.

1. These competencies need to be formed in each lesson, and as its effective factors: the teacher's creative approach to each lesson; the competence of the subject teacher and the need to increase students' motivation to study (interest, desire, desire, dedication).

In order to effectively organize the teaching of physics departments in higher education institutions, first of all, it is necessary to plan the teaching process in advance.

For this, it is appropriate to put on the agenda of higher education institutions the questions "Why is the Physics Department taught?", "What is learned in it?", "How should it be taught?", "What should be used to teach?" in order to achieve new competence. The goal of teaching physics

in higher technical educational institutions is to educate a person with formed knowledge, skills, qualifications and competence, with intellectual potential. The goal is the product of achieving a predetermined result, which is the achievement of high efficiency as a result of the joint activities of its subjects (teacher and student) in the educational process

Conclusion. The goal is the product of achieving a predetermined result, which is the advance guarantee of the planned acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities as a result of the joint activities of its subjects (teacher and student) in the educational process, providing constant assistance to the student in the process of independent acquisition, understanding, and development of knowledge and convincing him of this;

In accordance with the efforts made by our President in the field of modernization of the educational process in higher educational institutions, the main way to introduce modern pedagogical technologies into the classroom based on a communicative approach in teaching each subject is to abandon the outdated teaching system, which hinders the increase in educational efficiency.

Based on this, it is a requirement of today to develop projects for each lesson of the physics department in higher education institutions based on the principles of pedagogical technology in the field of communicative approach and implement them in the educational process.

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